

THE POTENTIAL OF BACTERIOPHAGE THERAPY AS AN ALTERNATIVE TREATMENT FOR ANTIBIOTIC-RESISTANT INFECTIONS

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Introduction

Bacteriophages, or phages, are viruses found abundantly in the environment and have the ability to infect, replicate within, and ultimately destroy bacteria in a highly specific manner during their lytic phase. Unlike antibiotics, phages have a much narrower host range, making them a promising supplement or even alternative to antibiotic therapy, particularly when combating multiple drug-resistant (MDR) bacterial infections, where antibiotics often fail. The concept of bacteriophage therapy is not new. In fact, bacteriophages were first identified in the early 20th century, with Felix d'Herelle pioneering their therapeutic use after British bacteriologist Frederick W. Twort first described bacterial lysis in 1915. The former Soviet Union consistently used phages to treat infections like gastrointestinal diseases and gas gangrene in soldiers. However, in the Western world, phage therapy fell out of favor following the discovery of penicillin after World War II.

The overuse of antibiotics in medicine, agriculture, and animal farming during the "golden era" of antibiotics has led to a significant rise in MDR bacteria, now a critical global health issue. Currently, MDR bacterial infections are responsible for approximately 1.27 million deaths annually worldwide, and it is estimated that this number could rise to 10 million by 2050. Given the diminishing effectiveness of traditional antibiotics, the re-emergence of bacteriophages, bacteria's natural predators, offers a potential solution to this growing public health crisis.

Despite their previous widespread use, there has been relatively little scientific research on bacteriophage therapy in recent decades. As a result, most of the current evidence regarding its safety and efficacy comes from case reports, preclinical studies, and a limited number of early randomized controlled trials (RCTs), which still present certain limitations.

This bibliometric analysis aims to provide an in-depth overview of the existing literature on the therapeutic use of bacteriophages. It also seeks to highlight ongoing efforts to establish a robust evidence base through RCTs, while assessing both the potential benefits and challenges of reviving this historical yet promising treatment approach.

Keywords: Bacteriophages, Phage therapy, Randomized-controlled trials.

Methods

Bibliometric Analysis

Data for this bibliometric analysis were obtained from the Web of Science (WoS) database, specifically from the SCI-Expanded sub-database. WoS covers a broad range of approximately 34,000 journals, with over 75 million records, including resources like the Science Citation Index, Social Sciences Citation Index, Arts and Humanities Citation Index, Conference Proceedings Citation Index, Book Citation Index, and Emerging Sources Citation Index. The Thomas Scientific impact factor is also derived from data within the WoS database.

The search was conducted using the keywords: "bacteriophage" OR "phage" AND "therapy" OR "application." Articles published between January 1, 1965, and December 31,

2023, were included, with no language restrictions. To ensure relevance and accuracy, two authors independently reviewed the titles and abstracts to confirm alignment with the research topic.

Data were extracted in January 2024, and the information was exported in plain text format and organized into tables. The extracted data included publication year, total citations, citations per year, author affiliations, journal publications, subject areas, article types, and countries of origin.

Results

Bibliometric Analysis

A total of 6,355 articles were included in the analysis, which collectively received 215,209 citations (157,789 excluding self-citations), resulting in an average of 33.9 citations per article and an H-index of 178. Over the last decade, the number of publications on bacteriophage therapy has more than tripled, increasing from 212 articles in 2011 to 739 articles in 2023. The majority of these articles were written in English (98.9%), with smaller contributions in French (0.3%) and German (0.2%). Most of the publications were original research articles (4,886, 76.8%), followed by reviews (1,187, 18.7%) and editorials (131, 2.1%). The remaining publications consisted of meeting abstracts, proceedings, book chapters, and letters to the editor. These articles were distributed across 923 different journals (Table 1). A total of 24,005 distinct authors contributed to the literature, with the highest proportion of articles coming from the USA (28.2%), followed by China (16.0%), the UK (7.8%), Germany (7.5%), and Poland (5.1%).

Systematic Review

A systematic search of PubMed, using the filter "randomized controlled trial," identified 44 articles for potential retrieval. Of these, only 7 articles met the eligibility criteria for inclusion, involving a total of 418 participants. Mild to moderate adverse events related to phage therapy were reported in 10 out of 195 participants (5.1%) across three studies. One study tested phages in healthy participants. The treatment indications in these studies included bacterial diarrhea, urinary tract infections, infected burn wounds, chronic otitis, chronic venous leg ulcers, and chronic rhinosinusitis. Three of the studies demonstrated a statistically significant difference in outcomes when comparing single-phage therapy to the standard of care or placebo.

Discussion

The goal of this bibliometric analysis was to provide an overview of the current state of the literature regarding the therapeutic use of bacteriophages. Our findings show a clear upward trend in citations on this topic, suggesting that phage therapy is gaining significant attention within the research community.

The most frequently cited paper in our analysis was published in 2001. It reviewed studies conducted in Poland and the former Soviet Union, comparing phages with antibiotics and addressing early challenges in phage therapy research. This work paved the way for future advancements in the therapeutic application of phages. The second and third most cited publications also explored the potential of phages. Notably, the 2007 study by Lu and Collins demonstrated the effectiveness of engineered phages in biofilm removal, highlighting the practicality of synthetic biology for manipulating these viruses. Additionally, Schooley and colleagues detailed methods for designing therapeutic phage cocktails and developing

personalized treatments for diabetic patients with necrotizing pancreatitis complicated by MDR *Acinetobacter baumannii* infections.

One of the main barriers to the widespread implementation of phage therapy has been the limited availability of clinical data regarding its safety and efficacy. Out of an initial pool of 6,355 articles, only 7 randomized controlled trials (RCTs) were identified, involving a total of 418 participants. Consequently, much of the current evidence is derived from case studies, with over 2,200 applications of phage therapy in hard-to-treat infections reported. This discrepancy may be attributed to regulatory constraints, as phage therapy remains classified as an unapproved medical product under Article 37 of the World Medical Association's Declaration of Helsinki. The personalized nature of phage therapy, along with challenges in accessing effective phages, has further limited the availability of clinical data.

Additionally, issues such as intellectual property concerns and a lack of interest from pharmaceutical companies have slowed the advancement of phage therapy. To overcome these obstacles, it may be necessary for government sectors to step in, creating a more favorable investment climate for pharmaceutical companies or offering greater support to research initiatives. Such measures could promote collaboration and stimulate further exploration, potentially accelerating the development of phage therapy and its incorporation into mainstream medical practice.

Limitations

Bibliometric analysis is a useful tool for assessing research impact, influence, and trends, but it comes with several limitations that must be considered. First, the analysis is based solely on published studies, which may lead to an incomplete view of the total research activity in the field of phage therapy. Unpublished or gray literature, such as conference proceedings, might not be included. Additionally, the search in the Web of Science (WoS) database focuses on citations, abstracts, and keywords, which could result in the omission of relevant articles that only mention the key terms in their methods sections. This limitation may affect the comprehensiveness of the list of identified articles on phage therapy.

Furthermore, the analysis is based on citation counts alone, which may not necessarily reflect the quality of the research. Factors like the age of the study, the journal in which it was published, and whether it is open-access can all influence citation counts. Therefore, the results might not fully represent the true quality of the research. It is important to recognize that a study with fewer citations might be of higher quality than one with a larger citation count.

Conclusions

In summary, phage therapy has gained increasing attention as a potential complement to antibiotics in recent years. While randomized controlled trials (RCTs) across various indications have demonstrated the safety of phage therapy, the lack of robust *in vivo* evidence remains a key obstacle to its broader acceptance. These limitations are often linked to issues with study design. Additionally, a deeper understanding of phage pharmacology is essential, as it often poses challenges to the effective clinical application of phages. For phage therapy to be successfully integrated into clinical practice, researchers and clinicians must learn from past experiences and rigorously address critical aspects in future trials, such as phage preparation quality, sensitivity testing, titers and dosages, access to infection sites, and

stability. Furthermore, the establishment of standardized treatment protocols will be essential to optimize the efficacy of phage therapy.

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